

1 Observation of multi-directional energy transfer
2 in a hybrid plasmonic-excitonic nanostructure
3 Supplementary Information

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Data	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis	Median
Area	89.67 nm ²	93.93 nm ²	8823.18 nm ⁴	2.92	12.62	63.08 nm ²
Major	12.86 nm	7.38 nm ²	54.52 nm ²	1.07	0.61	10.87 nm
Minor	7.39 nm	3.43 nm	11.73nm ²	1.72	8.39	6.88 nm
Angle	92.90°	55.63°	3094.61 ° ²	-0.09	-1.29	92.72°
Circ.	0.72	0.19	0.04	-0.84	-0.31	0.78
AR	1.79	0.77	0.59	1.91	4.62	1.58

Table S1: Table reporting the values of the statistical analysis of particle shape. The total number of particles examined is 261, as observed in the overview image inset in S1. In each row, all the statistical parameters are reported for: nanoparticle area, the major and minor axis of the best fitting ellipse, the angle from horizontal of the best fitting ellipse major axis, the degree of circularity and the aspect ratio.

1 Transmission electron microscopy and particle shape analysis

High resolution Transmission electron studies were performed in an aberration corrected JEOL - ARM200F, working at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. The samples were mounted in a reinforced beryllium holder (JEOL) and left in dark conditions and vacuum over night. Images were collected with a zone axis WSe₂ [0,0,1].

The following analysis shows that the Au covered area fraction is 50%, and that in-plane particle size follows a skewed distribution whose median is 10 nm. The nominal thickness of the nanoparticles is estimated to be around 2 nm. The epitaxial relationship is evident from the static diffractogram reported in Fig. 1d of the main text, where single crystalline Bragg peaks from Au are observed as a replica for each WSe₂ substrate peak. The slight offset between the peaks results from the mismatch between the two lattice structures that, combined with the large inelastic mean free path of Au atoms on WSe₂ surface, is at the origin of the Vollmer-Weber growth resulting in the self-assembled nanostructures [1].

The particle shape analysis was performed using a TEM microscopy image from the same sample and instrument as in Fig. 1d of the main article. The image spans a range of 180 nm x 213 nm. The image has been thresholded to define the islands. The result is reported in the inset in Fig. S1. The Au islands are in white. The area and circularity of the nanoparticles were extracted using the ImageJ automated analysis software. Circularity is given by $4\pi * Area / (Perimeter)^2$. The nanoparticles were also fitted with ellipses, allowing to extract several parameters: major and minor axes, the angle of the major axis with respect to the horizontal (Angle), and the aspect ratio. The results are summarized in Tab. S1 and Fig. S1.

From Tab. S1, emerges a simplified average shape of thin, ellipsoidal disks with major axis around 13 nm and minor axis around 7 nm, elongated in randomly oriented directions. By looking at the distributions of Fig. S1, however, it is clear that the sizes and shapes of the nanostructures span a vast range of scales, thus making necessary a true-to-shape finite-element modelling, as reported in Fig. S2.

2 Localized fields and finite elements calculations

We report the distribution of the field enhancement $|E|/|E_0|$ (where $|E|$ is the modulus of the electric field in the heterostructure and $|E_0|$ is the field in absence of Au). This scalar quantity is calculated by performing finite element, frequency domain calculations on a model

Figure S1: Violin plot showing the distributions of the values of each parameter. The vertical scale of each distribution has been normalized to the mean value, reported in Tab. S1. The "range" axis thus represents the extent of the distribution in units of the mean value. The thick line encloses the range between 25% and 75% of the mean value, while the thin line marks the range within 1.5 times the interquartile range.

73 Au/WSe₂ heterostructure (see also Methods in the main article). The dielectric functions
 74 were from tabulated data: Au from [2] and WSe₂ from [3]. To calculate $|E_0|$, the calculation
 75 was repeated with identical settings except for the refractive and absorption index of Au,
 76 that were set to the ones of vacuum instead. The total modulus was calculated for both
 77 E and E_0 3D vector fields, and their ratio determined to produce the three-dimensional
 78 scalar field of field enhancement. The field is then sampled by slicing the model volume
 79 with a plane parallel to the Au/WSe₂ interface. In the following images, we report the field
 80 enhancement on two planes above and below the interface at various different wavelengths.

81 The slices above the surface (Fig. S2 a,c,e,g,i) show the field enhancement within the
 82 nanoislands and in the vacuum space between them. At 400 nm the excitation frequency is
 83 above the Au interband transtion, Au absorption becomes significant, and the field enhance-
 84 ments are largely confined outside of the nanoparticles. With longer wavelengths, we observe
 85 significant field enhancement also within the nanoparticles as the bulk shape of the particle
 86 becomes more relevant in determining the dominant plasmonic modes. In the 800-1030 nm
 87 range explored in the experiments, the generation of hot electrons is therefore enhanced by
 88 localized plasmonic excitations that affect a large fraction of the volume of the particle and
 89 depend strongly on the particle shape. The slices below the surface (Fig. S2 b,d,f,h,j), on
 90 the other hand, indicate how the field tailoring produced by the nanostructure propagates
 91 within the WSe₂ substrate. Above the semiconducting direct bandgap, the field enhance-

Figure S2: **Electric field enhancement at various wavelengths.** a.-b. Electric field enhancement in Au nanoislands on WSe₂ 2 nm above (a.) and 1 nm below (b.) the interface, with 400 nm excitation. c.-d. Same, but for 800 nm excitation. e.-f. Same, but for 860 nm excitation. g.-h. Same but for 1060 nm excitation. i.-j. Same, but for 1200 nm excitation.

92 ments within WSe₂ are small. At 400 nm light is strongly absorbed also by the nanoparticles,
 93 and we observe only weak enhancement in the gaps between them (Fig. S2 b). At 800 nm,
 94 the particles act as field concentrators and a weak enhancement is created under their foot-
 95 print (Fig. S2 d). At longer wavelengths the enhanced field can propagate more freely in
 96 the semiconductor, and we observe large field enhancements generated by the edges of the
 97 particles whose shape resonate with the excitation wavelength (Fig. S2 f,h,i). This there-
 98 fore suggests that, as we move towards longer wavelengths, we increase the probability for
 99 multiphoton processes in the semiconductor due to large field enhancements.

100 3 Band structure calculations with density functional theory

101 For the overlaid curves in Fig. 2b (main article) and Fig. S4 c, we performed density func-
 102 tional theory (DFT) calculation of WSe₂ and Au with the projector augmented wave code
 103 GPAW [4] using GLLBSE xc-functional, separately. The GLLBSC is an orbital-dependent
 104 exact exchange-based functional that is well suited for the description of noble metals [5, 6].
 105 While DFT+U might provide a better description of the d-states of Au, we opted for a
 106 parameter-free functional that still provides a good description of the plasmonic proper-
 107 ties [7], as the d-bands are not involved in the dynamics discussed in this work. For Au,
 108 we performed a slab calculation, with 5 ML Au(111) (2.5 nm) thickness and 15 Å vacuum
 109 thickness. The choice of a slab calculation allowed us to obtain an ab-initio description of

110 the Shockley surface state. We used a Monkhorst-Pack sampling of the Brillouin zone with
 111 (12x12x1) points. The plane wave energy cutoff was at 600 eV, the occupation defined by
 112 a Fermi-Dirac distribution with 0.01 eV width. For WSe₂, we performed a bulk calculation
 113 with (12x12x12) Monkhorst-Pack sampling, plane wave energy cutoff at 600 eV and occupa-
 114 tion defined by a Fermi-Dirac distribution with 0.01 eV width. The bandpath was selected
 115 to cut the Brillouin zone at $k_z=0$. All DFT calculations are performed with the projector
 116 augmented wave code GPAW using fully relativistic - thus including spin-orbit coupling -
 117 plane wave basis sets and PAW potentials version 0.9.2.

118 4 Weak hybridization of the electronic states

119 Besides the general agreement to the DFT calculations for the two separate materials re-
 120 ported in Fig.2 b and Fig. S4 c, we have attempted to further investigate the effects of
 121 interfacing on the electronic structure of the two materials.

122 The first evidence is the absence of any variation in the shape of the core-level peaks
 123 shown in Fig. S4 a,b, which would display the evolution of substructures arising from different
 124 valence states of the atoms in the presence of alloying, chemical bonding or oxidation. The
 125 peaks of Selenium (not shown), were also measured and do not show any significant lineshape
 126 change.

127 Furthermore, it is possible to inspect the valence band with a more critical insight. Two
 128 features have been identified in [8], where monolayers of MoS₂ on bulk Au(111) were studied,
 129 that showed a deviation between the suspended theoretical bandstructure of ML MoS₂ and
 130 the one observed on the Au(111) substrate.

131 The first is a flattening and shift towards lower binding energies of the band at the Γ point.
 132 This phenomenon arises because the orbital character in this region is formed predominantly
 133 by the chalcogenide p_z orbitals and transition metal d_{z^2} and d_{yz} orbitals, and is therefore
 134 sensitive to out-of-plane chemical interactions. In [8], the MoS₂ valence band top at Γ is
 135 found to be shifted 310 meV to higher binding energies due to hybridization with Au d-band
 136 continuum. No such effect is observed in the present case of thin Au(111) overlayers on
 137 WSe₂, as demonstrated by Fig. S3 a,b.

138 Another region where the effects of interfacing are seen is the M point. Indeed this repre-
 139 sents a time-reversal invariant momentum point, where the combination of crystal symmetry
 140 and time-reversal symmetry enforce spin degeneracy. The lowest binding energy band, that
 141 is spin-orbit split at the K points, is therefore degenerate at the M point. In the case of
 142 ML MoS₂ on Au, such degeneracy is not observed, owing to the suppression of momentum-
 143 matching constraints at the edge of the Brillouin zone caused by strong hybridization with
 144 the Au states. In the present case, the band at the M point appears to be spin degenerate
 145 as shown in Fig. S3 c,d.

146 5 Core-level photoemission and band alignment

147 The band alignment between Au and WSe₂ can be explored with very precise insight using
 148 photoemission data. Firstly, we consider the shifting of the core levels. We measure the
 149 Au 4f and W 4f peaks for the separate surfaces of Au(111) and WSe₂(0001), and for the
 150 heterostructure. To gain a deeper insight in the effects of Au coverage, we also measured at
 151 two different nominal Au thicknesses, 12 Å and 36 Å. The results are reported in Fig. S4.

Figure S3: **Weak interaction modifications of the electronic structure.** a. Static bandstructure cut along the K- Γ -K direction. Red line shows the EDC cut shown in panel b. b. EDC cuts at the Γ point for bare WSe_2 (black) and Au/WSe_2 (red). The red EDC has been shifted by 122 meV to compensate the effects of band alignment. c. Static bandstructure along the K-M-K direction. The yellow and red lines show the respective EDC cuts shown in panel d. d. EDC cuts at M (red) and slightly off M (yellow), showing how, moving toward the M point, the double peaked structure around 2 eV becomes a spin-degenerate feature around 2.5 eV.

152 Considering the electron affinity $X_{\text{WSe}_2}=4.1$ eV, the Fermi edge position $\Phi=4.4$ eV, and
 153 the indirect bandgap $E_g=1.47$ eV, in a freshly cleaved WSe_2 (0001) surface the virtual Fermi
 154 edge position is just 300 meV below the conduction band minimum, in line with the n-type
 155 behaviour observed for intrinsic WSe_2 . In this condition, contacting the Au(111) facet, of
 156 work function $\Phi_{\text{Au}}=5.5$ eV, would cause a shift of the Fermi level in WSe_2 of $\Delta\Phi=1.1$ eV.
 157 This would lead to the Fermi level being very close to the valence band, just 100-70 meV
 158 above. However, this is not what is observed. Indeed, we only observe a shift of 170 ± 5
 159 meV of the WSe_2 bands when Au is evaporated on the surface. This indicates that the
 160 band bending is strongly suppressed and the Fermi level is moved to only 0.47 eV below the
 161 conduction band.

162 Considering the Schottky-Mott theory of contact potential, the Fermi level would be
 163 expected to be energetically near the VBM. However, owing to the work function reduction
 164 observed in Au nanoparticles [9], the Fermi level is closer to the conduction band minimum
 165 of WSe_2 , with Schottky barrier $\Phi_e = 0.470 \pm 0.005$ eV for electrons (ESB) and $\Phi_h = 1.000 \pm$
 166 0.005 eV for holes (HSB) [10].

167 Such suppression results from the nanoscale structure of Au. In these conditions, the

Figure S4: **Band alignment.** a. Au 4f_{7/2} peak at room temperature for bulk Au(111), for 12 Å Au on WSe₂ and for 36 Å Au on WSe₂. Dashed line marks the reference for Bulk. Black markers indicate peak position as obtained by fitting with Doniach-Sunjić lineshape convolved with a Gaussian. b. W 4f doublet at room temperature for freshly cleaved WSe₂(0001), and the heterostructure at two coverages reported in panel a. Dashed vertical line marks the reference for the bulk, black markers indicate the peak position as obtained by fitting Voigt lineshapes. c. Combined image of static ARPES, a time-resolved ARPES snapshot at t=20 fs (inset), and bandstructure calculations. note that the tr-ARPES snapshot has been aligned energetically considering the fact that the Fermi edge is shifted by -40 meV in the transient signal.

168 nanoparticles have a significantly reduced work function. This is clear from the Au 4f shifts
 169 in Fig. S4 a. When 12 Å Au are deposited on WSe₂ surface, the 4f_{7/2} peak shifts about
 170 -420 ± 8 meV to higher binding energies, owing to the reduced work function. Upon further
 171 increase of the thickness to 36 Å, the film still remains disconnected, but the islands grow,
 172 thus getting closer to the bulk work function: the Au 4f shift decreases to -220 ± 7 meV. Au
 173 4f peak positions are determined by fitting the 4f_{7/2} with a Doniach-Sunjić lineshape, after
 174 Shirley background subtraction of the whole 4f doublet. Errors are propagated from the
 175 standard deviation on the fit result.

176 As the islands are disconnected, a static electric dipole also builds at the interface, that
 177 further contributes to the band bending suppression. This is clear from the monotonous
 178 positive shifting of the W 4f peaks in Fig. S4 b: at 12 Å, it is $+270 \pm 8$ meV, while at
 179 36 Å, it is $+440 \pm 9$ meV. W 4f peak positions are determined by fitting the 4f_{7/2} with a
 180 Voigt lineshape, after Shirley background subtraction of the whole 4f doublet. Errors are
 181 propagated from the standard deviation on the fit result.

182 It does not appear that Au evaporation produces significant chemical interaction with
 183 WSe₂, as the core-level lineshapes are remarkably identical to each other, aside from the
 184 aforementioned shifts. There are also no significant hints of hybridization in the bandstruc-
 185 ture, as explained in the previous section.

186 Finally, we have one more method to pinpoint the band alignment, i.e. the use of time-
 187 resolved ARPES. As it can be readily seen in the overlay of Fig. S4 c, the Fermi edge is indeed
 188 about 0.5 eV away from the bottom of the conduction band. More precisely, we find the

189 valence band minimum 612 ± 2 meV above the Fermi edge. However, we have to consider that
 190 at the time delay in which we have sufficient population of the bands (reported in the inset
 191 in Fig. S4 c) we also have a transient relative shifting of the charge state of the two materials,
 192 that adds up to 140 ± 5 meV (see Fig.3a). The equilibrium position of the conduction band
 193 minimum is therefore 472 ± 5 meV above the Fermi level, and this constitutes the electron
 194 Schottky barrier.

195 6 Lifetime of Σ valley population

196 To perform the fits of the Σ valley population, we built a fitting function that consists of a
 197 double exponential decay convolved with a gaussian instrument response function.

198 This allowed us to isolate the intrinsic and interfacing-dependent timescales. We first con-
 199 sidered a dataset measured for the WSe₂ bare surface in the same experimental conditions,
 200 but with a much wider delay range, up to 200 ps. Fitting the population of the Σ valley
 201 with the convolved double exponential (with fixed gaussian FWHM of 40 fs), returned two
 202 timescales: 1502 ± 78 fs and 31 ± 2 ps. The result is reported in Fig. S5.

203 The first time-constant seems rather short with respect to the dark exciton lifetime or
 204 defect recombination times reported in literature [11]. It thus might be attributable to dark
 205 exciton diffusion in the bulk, away from the probing depth of ARPES.

206 In the dataset discussed in the main text, the delay range is much smaller, so only the
 207 short timescale is relevant. It is evident from the data, however, that a second, shorter
 208 timescale arises in the heterostructure. We thus considered the curve of Au/WSe₂ at low
 209 temperature, showing the fastest dynamics. By fixing the longest timescale to be 1502 fs, we
 210 obtain the shortest to be 240 ± 28 fs. The amplitude of the fast decay is $72\pm 2\%$ of the signal.
 211 These two timescales are sufficient to fit the other two curves in Fig.3c with high reliability
 212 by only changing the ratio between them. The one for Au/WSe₂ at RT is fitted by reducing
 213 the short timescale to the $36\pm 8\%$ of the signal, while the pure WSe₂ converges with only
 214 $2\pm 10\%$ of the short timescale, indicating that it is well fitted by the single exponential of
 215 1.5 ps.

216 7 Fluence dependence of Σ valley population

217 We discuss here the procedure to extract data from the 1030 nm pump dataset. The mea-
 218 surement was performed at fixed delay of +400 fs, i.e. after the ultrafast charge transfer
 219 mechanisms have taken place, thus in the condition to observe the exciton population gener-
 220 ated in WSe₂ by two photon processes. The fluence was changed from 0.28 to 2.34 mJ/cm².

221 In these conditions, the electronic temperature is between 1500-2000 K and, while still
 222 lower than 5800 K (the minimum electron Schottky barrier, which also increases transiently),
 223 this is sufficient to produce a background signal from the Au electrons that needs to be
 224 removed in order to isolate the Σ valley population.

225 The shape of the Au bands in the momentum region corresponding to the WSe₂ sigma
 226 valley (between the red lines in Fig. S6 b) is such that a fluence dependent fit of the Fermi
 227 edge is not reliable at high fluences. For this reason, an exponential decay background was
 228 used above the Fermi level. A typical result is shown in Fig. S6 a. However, given the
 229 less physically solid choice of fitting function, a routine was employed to improve statistical

Figure S5: **Long delay Σ valley population for pure WSe₂.** Combination of data and fit for pure WSe₂ measured with 800 nm pump, 0.6 mJ/cm² fluence. The long delay range shows a two timescales decay.

230 accuracy: for each point of the fluence dependence, the background fitting and subtraction
 231 was repeated six times, with slightly different choices of fitting intervals. The error bar in the
 232 data reported in Fig.3d are determined as the standard deviation of the result distribution.

233 Fermi edge extraction was instead carried out in the momentum range corresponding to
 234 the sp-band, marked by black lines in Fig. S6 b. In this region, the Fermi distribution could
 235 be fitted reliably at all fluences, and the error reported is the standard deviation obtained
 236 by least square fitting.

237 Finally, we report here a plot of the integral of the Fermi-Dirac electron distribution above
 238 the energy levels corresponding to the Σ and K valleys. If we exclude the lowest fluence,
 239 that produces a negligible increase in the electronic temperature, and fails to produce a
 240 detectable population above the WSe₂ valence band energy, as the hot electron population

Figure S6: **Analysis of 1030 nm measurements.** a. Typical result of background fitting for the extraction of fluence dependence of Σ valley population. The fluence is 1.66 mJ/cm^2 , the delay $+400 \text{ fs}$. The red circles show the data as obtained from tr-ARPES signal integration in the momentum range shown in panel b by the red lines. The blue curve shows the exponential background. b. tr-ARPES map with 1030 nm pumping. The red lines mark the range of integration for the EDC used for Σ valley population extraction, while the black lines show the range for Fermi edge fitting. c. Plot of the integral of the Fermi-Dirac distribution between the energy of the Σ and K valley and infinity, as a function of the electronic temperatures corresponding to the fluences used in Fig.3d.

241 scales linearly in this range of fluences.

242 8 Negligibility of Seebeck effect and surface photovoltage

243 Regarding the shifts observed in Fig. 3b, we have examined if they result from a combination
 244 of surface photovoltage and Seebeck effect (transient voltages due to transient temperature
 245 gradients). Both effects can be ruled out.

246 On Bare WSe_2 the bands shift by less than 7 meV in any condition of fluence, pump
 247 wavelength and temperature, thus ruling out any intrinsic effects of the semiconductor. The
 248 effect is also too short-lived with respect to classic surface photovoltage.

249 The Fermi edge of Au does not shift due to temperature changes. This is what is measured
 250 by the Seebeck coefficient, which for Au is below $3 \mu\text{V/K}$ up to 2500K. This means that
 251 a change of temperature of 3000 K results in a shift of less than 9 meV. We observe shifts
 252 of 20 meV (electronic temperature change $\Delta T_e=700 \text{ K}$, Seebeck shift 2 meV), or 40 meV
 253 ($\Delta T_e=800 \text{ K}$, Seebeck shift 2.4 meV) or finally of 200 meV ($\Delta T_e=3000 \text{ K}$, Seebeck shift 9
 254 meV).

255 9 Energy flow across the interface

256 The band alignment suggests that under photoexcitation with photon energies below the
 257 Au interband threshold ($<2 \text{ eV}$) plasmon-generated hot electrons can be injected at much
 258 larger rates than hot holes thus dominating the charge transfer mechanism. The still sizable

259 Schottky barrier suppresses the diffusion of thermalized electrons across the interface for low
 260 photoexcitation fluences ($<10 \text{ mJ/cm}^2$).

261 At higher pump photon energies, it becomes possible to excite large populations of deep
 262 lying holes with long lifetimes, giving rise to complex energy exchanges that may tip the
 263 balance in favour of hot-hole injection [12, 13], but this falls beyond the scope of our work.
 264 We will restrict our discussion to pump photon energies below the A exciton resonance of
 265 bulk WSe₂ (1.626 eV at room temperature [14]).

266 A simple electrostatic calculation considering the peak chemical potential shift $\Delta E = 40$
 267 meV and the nanoparticle capacitance $C = 3 \text{ aF}$ allows to calculate the net number of injected
 268 electrons as $n = \Delta E \cdot C \leq 1$. Combining this with the number of absorbed photons per
 269 nanoparticle at 800 nm, considering an absorption of 0.1% of the nanoparticles (from the
 270 FDTD calculations), we get a quantum efficiency (in gap photon to hot electron in WSe₂)
 271 of about 2%, in line with other reports on similar systems. We argue, however, that the
 272 flow of energy carried by unbalanced charges is smaller than the total energy flow across the
 273 interface, owing to the fact that both HSB and ESB are smaller than the photon energy at
 274 any pump excitation wavelength.

275 10 Probing depth of ARPES

276 When considering photoemission data from a heterogeneous sample, it is important to re-
 277 member that the probing depth of ARPES is extremely short, in the range 10-5 Å at the
 278 photon energies employed in the current experiment (21.7 eV). This means that the exper-
 279 iment is predominantly sensitive to the top facet of the Au islands and the open areas of
 280 WSe₂, while the interface between the islands and the semiconductor is more challenging to
 281 access experimentally.

282 Our analysis overcomes this hurdle in two ways. Firstly, we focused on observables that
 283 do not require the direct observation of the spatial region below the particle. The band
 284 alignment analysis is supported to a very high degree of consistency by core-level data
 285 (more bulk sensitive) and theoretical calculations. The dynamics is explored considering
 286 the electronic temperature of Au, its chemical potential, the band positions in WSe₂, i.e.
 287 properties that can be considered homogeneous at the scale of a single particle or gap (approx.
 288 10 nm) at these timescales ($\lesssim 10 \text{ fs}$). Secondly, to assess for example population dynamics,
 289 we put ourselves in a condition where we are intrinsically selective of the carriers generated
 290 by injection by tuning the excitation wavelength.

291 The latter strategy is viable because the signal does carry information on the WSe₂ Bloch
 292 eigenfunctions below the islands, at least to a degree. A careful comparison of the MDCs
 293 of the bands of bare WSe₂ to the same states in the heterostructure, shows that they are
 294 broadened to a FWHM of 0.1 Å^{-1} . This corresponds, in real space, to approx. 10 nm, i.e. the
 295 average gap between the islands, suggesting that, in a three-step picture of photoemission,
 296 the confinement of the ARPES wavefunction happens in the final step. The information
 297 carried by the angular distribution of the photoelectrons, however, relates to the coherence
 298 length of the electron wavepacket in the solid within the plane. In this direction, the inelastic
 299 mean free path of the electrons is rather large, and no significant losses are encountered at
 300 such energies. Therefore, while the signal arising from below the nanoparticles might be
 301 suppressed, the ARPES signal should still carry information regarding the interface.

11 Non-thermal electrons

As discussed in [15], in the femtoseconds immediately subsequent optical excitation the electronic distribution in the proximity of the Fermi edge assumes a shape that is not described by a Fermi-Dirac distribution. It is instead formed by a Fermi-Dirac distribution of higher temperature, with superimposed steps with exactly the width of the photon energy $\hbar\omega$. A step-wise decrease in the range $[E_f - \hbar\omega, E_f]$ as electronic states below the Fermi level are depleted, and a step-wise increase in the range $[E_f, E_f + \hbar\omega]$. The steps might have a more complicated structure, arising from the details of the DOS of the metal within $\hbar\omega$ from the Fermi level. Aluminum, for example, is theoretically predicted to display a small peak in each step, owing to a local maximum in the DOS just below E_f . The DOS of Au, instead, is rather flat until 2 eV below E_f , thus producing flat, step-like features. We investigate the existence of such non-equilibrium distributions for two reasons: to ensure that large non-thermal distributions of electrons do not affect our fitting of the Fermi edge (in particular the energy position), and to understand the role of non-thermal electronic distributions in the early dynamics of the heterostructure.

As can be seen in Fig. S7, both the fits of the Fermi edge return no significant non-thermal contributions superimposed on the Fermi-Dirac distribution. The fits have been performed by fitting a Fermi-Dirac distribution convolved with a Gaussian distribution to simulate experimental distribution. The width of the Gaussian was obtained by fitting the negative delays while constraining the temperature to be 70 K, and found to be 150 meV. Then, the Fermi edge was fit leaving the amplitude, the energy position and the temperature as free parameters. The fits of the sp-band have been performed in a rather restricted energy range to avoid contamination of the signal with the intensity of WSe₂ conduction band K points.

The lack of obvious non-thermal distributions, or in general of strong trends in the residuals of the fits, indicates that the fitted Fermi edge position discussed in the manuscript is reliable. More subtle is the interpretation of the role of non-thermal populations in the dynamics of the heterostructure. While we would expect to observe non-equilibrium distributions at these incident fluences and delay ranges, their absence might suggest that all hot carriers are injected in the semiconductor. However, to assess the non-thermal component of the electronic distribution directly, it would be necessary to have a signal-to-noise ratio in the residuals much higher than the one of the current experiment. Such dedicated experiment falls beyond the scope of the current work.

12 Two temperature model for electron-lattice equilibration in Au

In Fig. 3a of the main article we compare the experimental results to the prediction of the two temperature model (2TM)[16, 17]. A simple two temperature model was set-up to create a reference of bulk Au without charge-transfer, in the same conditions of excitation density. The equations employed are:

$$(\gamma_e \cdot T_e) \cdot \frac{dT_e}{dt} = -G_{e-ph}(T_e - T_l) + P(t) \quad (1)$$

$$C_l \cdot \frac{dT_l}{dt} = G_{el-ph}(T_e - T_l) \quad (2)$$

Figure S7: **Fits of the Fermi edge.** a. Surface state Fermi edge dynamics map showing an EDC for every delay. EDCs are extracted integrating k_x $[-0.5, 0.5]$ and k_y $[-0.5, 0.5]$ to encompass the Shockley surface state. b. Residuals at each delay, the image colorscale has been scaled to cover $\pm 0.5\%$ of the Fermi edge amplitude. c. Representative EDC (red, solid line) with Fermi edge fit (blue solid line). d. Fermi edge dynamics map showing an EDC for every delay. EDCs are extracted integrating a range including the sp-band. e. Residuals at each delay, the image colorscale has been scaled to cover $\pm 0.3\%$ of the Fermi edge amplitude. f. Representative EDC (red, solid line) with Fermi edge fit (blue solid line).

with

$$P(t) = \frac{A}{\Delta t/2 \cdot \sqrt{\pi/\ln(2)}} \cdot e^{-\frac{4\ln(2)(t-t_0)^2}{\Delta t^2}} \quad (3)$$

values of the parameters are $\gamma_e = 70 \text{ Jm}^{-3}\text{K}^{-2}$, $G_{e-ph} = 3 \times 10^6 \text{ Wm}^{-3}\text{K}^{-1}$ at 300 K,
 $G_{e-ph} = 2 \times 10^6 \text{ Wm}^{-3}\text{K}^{-1}$ at 70 K, $C_l = 2.4 \times 10^6 \text{ JK}^{-1}$ at 300 K, $C_l = 2 \times 10^6 \text{ JK}^{-1}$,
 $A = 10^8 \text{ Vm}^{-1}$, $\Delta t = 36 \text{ fs}$.

13 Optical properties and thickness of free-standing WSe₂

For the FED experiments we have estimated the thickness of bare WSe₂ flakes from their optical properties (absorption spectrum). Subsequently, the thickness of the deposited Au

342 (with electron beam evaporation) was controlled with a quartz crystal microbalance.

Figure S8: **Fitting the absorption spectrum of bare WSe₂ flakes used for FED to extract the thickness.** (a) The experimental absorption spectrum of a bare WSe₂ represented with the calculated spectra for 20 nm and 30 nm thickness. (b) The sum of square errors (residuals) as a function of the thickness.

343 The values for the wavelength-dependent real (n) and imaginary (k) refractive indices
 344 of multilayer WSe₂ are taken from the work of Gu et al.[3]. The absorption spectrum
 345 is calculated with the transfer matrix method as a function of the WSe₂ thickness. The
 346 calculated spectra are compared with the experimental results (Fig. S8 a). The sum of
 347 square errors (residuals of the fitting) is minimized for a thickness of 20-25 nm (Fig. S8 b).

348 14 Extraction of MSD and lattice temperatures from FED

349 An example of a static diffraction pattern of the Au/WSe₂ heterostructures in logarithmic
 350 scale is shown in Fig. S9 a. The bright hexagonal pattern corresponds to single-crystalline,
 351 multilayer flakes of WSe₂. The less intense diffraction pattern corresponds to the epitaxially
 352 grown, (111)-oriented, nanoislands of Au (inset of Fig. S9 a). In the time-resolved experi-
 353 ments the lattice dynamics are initiated by femtosecond laser pulse pumping the electrons.
 354 The lattice dynamics are probed with ultrashort electron pulses at selected pump-probe de-
 355 lays. For each diffraction peak of WSe₂ we extract the relative intensity (Fig. S9 b) and
 356 subsequently the change of the atomic MSD (Fig. S9 c). For Au the temporal evolution
 357 of the MSD (Fig. S9 d) cannot be described by the single-exponential dynamics measured
 358 previously for bulk Au and Au nanoclusters on insulating substrates.

359 To confirm that sub-band-gap light does not induce any measurable lattice dynamics in
 360 bare WSe₂, we have performed the experiment shown in Fig. S10 a. First, we found spatial
 361 and temporal overlap of pump (850 nm) and probe (electrons), and then we moved to a bare
 362 WSe₂ flake and repeated the FED scan in the ± 20 ps range.

363 In contrast, sub-band-gap light initiates a strong lattice response for Au-decorated WSe₂
 364 flakes. An incident laser fluence of 0.97 mJ/cm² can cause a 410 K temperature rise of the
 365 Au nanoislands (Fig. S11 a). The representation of the temperature of evolution of Au with a

Figure S9: **FED of Au/WSe₂ heterostructures pumped at the A-exciton resonance.** (a) The electron diffraction pattern of Au/WSe₂ (logarithmic scale). The dark spots represent areas with high intensity of diffracted electrons. The two materials form two hexagonal patterns with strong and weak intensity of diffracted electrons belonging to WSe₂ and Au, respectively (see inset). (b) After excitation (Delay_i0) all diffraction peaks decay due to the Debye-Waller effect [18, 19]. The inset shows the index of each diffraction peak. (c) The intensity decay from each diffraction peak is used to extract the time-dependent atomic MSD of WSe₂ (same color code as in (a) and (b)) and the average of all peaks (green dot-line). (d) The time-dependent atomic MSD of Au following the same procedure. The solid lines represent exponential decay functions of various time-constants.

366 biexponential function is 20% more accurate, in terms of the sum of square errors, compared to a single exponential. The two processes have time-constants 4 ps and 16 ps and cause
 367 temperature rises of 90 and 310 K, respectively.
 368

369 Based on the results and discussions of the main article, the fast process is attributed to electron-phonon coupling in Au and the slow process to exciton dissociation. Fig. S11 b
 370 shows the temperature rises caused by the two processes as a function of the incident laser
 371 fluence. The solid lines are fittings with functions of the form $aF + bF^c$, where F is the
 372 fluence. Noticeably, as the fluence increases the heating of Au is dominated by exciton disso-
 373 ciation, while electron-phonon coupling in Au is suppressed. This observation corroborates
 374 our conclusion that plasmons and hot electrons in Au can induce nonlinear absorption and
 375

Figure S10: **No lattice response of bare WSe₂ flakes exposed to sub-band-gap light.** (a) The experiment used for finding temporal overlap of pump and probe and then testing the lattice dynamics of bare WSe₂. (b) The relative peak-decay for the (220) peak of a Au thin-film and for the average of the WSe₂ peaks.

Figure S11: **Lattice temperature evolution of Au nanoislands.** (a) Lattice temperature evolution of Au nanoislands on WSe₂ with sub-band-gap light. The experimental data (points) are fitted with a biexponential function (red) with time-constants 4 ps (orange) and 16 ps (blue). (b) The fluence dependent temperature rises of the fast and slow process, which are attributed to e-ph coupling and exciton dissociation, respectively.

³⁷⁶ rapid energy transfer into WSe₂.

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